

Numerical investigation of hydrogen isotope retention by an yttrium pebble-bed from flowing liquid lithium

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Abstract

Ensuring a secure and reliable execution of the International Fusion Materials Irradiation Facility (IFMIF) or the DEMO-Oriented Neutron Source (DONES) requires their liquid lithium loops to be purified from hydrogen isotopes which are generated during operation. In order to fulfil the demanded limits of protium, deuterium and tritium concentrations in the lithium, an yttrium pebble-bed will serve as a hydrogen hot trap. In the past, several theoretical studies have been executed with the purpose of estimating the hydrogen inventory build up in a lithium loop system, considering the trap as a black box with a constant or a concentration dependent efficiency. Disregarding the internal physical mechanisms which determine the retention process of a pebble-bed, these models are build on simplified assumptions and should be extended to allow a reliable hot trap design for IFMIF/DONES. For this purpose a detailed numerical model describing the hydrogen isotope transport from flowing liquid lithium into an yttrium pebble-bed is required and has been developed from scratch within the scope of this work using the software EcosimPro. It enables simulating the hydrogen isotope retention process into the getter material solving a system of coupled differential and algebraic equations. The model is used to simulate the temporal evolution of the hydrogen isotope concentrations and particle fluxes in a liquid lithium circuit that connects the inlet and outlet of an yttrium pebble-bed. In a case study different scenarios are simulated varying the boundary and initial conditions of the observed system. The outcomes of the simulation are presented in this work. For its validation the numerical model is used to reproduce measurement results of a previous deuterium retention experiment.

Keywords: IFMIF, DONES, tritium modelling, liquid lithium, yttrium pebble-bed, getter, hydrogen hot trap

1. Introduction

With the International Fusion Materials Irradiation Facility (IFMIF) and its reduced version the DEMO-Oriented Neutron Source (DONES) it is intended to investigate the property relevant effects high energetic neutron irradiation has on fusion relevant materials [1]. Generated by nuclear reactions between lithium atoms and a high energetic deuteron beam, the neutrons will reach energies similar to those expected at the first wall of future fusion power plants [2]. The lithium atoms move through a liquid lithium loop system where due to the occurring nuclear reactions and residual deuterium deposition, hydrogen isotopes are produced in a continuous manner. This leads to a linearly rising inventory of dissolved protium, deuterium and tritium in the loop. Due to corrosion between the lithium and the structural material of the loop further non-metallic impurities accumulate in the liquid lithium such as nitrogen, oxygen and carbon. All mentioned impurities and especially the inventory build-up of radioactive tritium are a threat for the plants safety and chemical stability. Hence, it needs to be ensured that their concentrations are kept below certain concentration limits. For this purpose the liquid lithium loop of IFMIF/DONES will be connected in parallel to a purification side loop system. The purification side loop consists of an impurity monitoring loop and an impurity control

system which are connected in parallel to the main loop. To remove the corrosion related non-metallic impurities a cold trap forms the first unit of the impurity control system. Connected in line with the cold trap an yttrium pebble-bed will serve as a hydrogen isotope hot trap [3]. Yttrium has a much higher solubility of hydrogen isotopes than lithium. This causes a transport of hydrogen isotopes into the pebbles which is driven by the laws of diffusion and the imbalance of the chemical potentials in the two systems. The design and operation of the hot trap will be mainly determined by the IFMIF/DONES safety regulations that require the tritium inventory in the lithium as well as in the yttrium to be kept below 0.3 g [4]. To ensure the fulfilment of the safety requirement it is essential to theoretically determine the most reasonable trap geometry, pebble-bed mass and pebble diameter for a certain system temperature. In former theoretical studies the retention behaviour of an yttrium pebble-bed was estimated, regarding the trap as a black box with an either constant or concentration dependant retention efficiency [5, 6]. However, models based on such simplified considerations do not allow reproducing or explaining experimental data with an accuracy that would be sufficient for a reliable trap design.

Therefore, a detailed numerical model describing the hydrogen transport from flowing liquid lithium into a bed of spherical yttrium pebbles is essential and has been developed from scratch within the scope of this work. In the model the govern-

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ing physical processes are represented by a system of coupled algebraic and differential equations. Since an exact analytical calculation of the temporal evolution of the system is not possible the differential equation solver and non-causal programming software EcosimPro is used as a numerical simulate tool [7]. EcosimPro allows component orientated programming, thus enabling a facilitated numerical calculation of the time evolution of hydrogen isotope concentrations and particle fluxes at numerous discrete locations in the described system. However, the reliability of the theoretical model is highly dependent on the accuracy of several material and flow specific experimental coefficients. Precisely measured temperature dependencies of the Sieverts' constant and the diffusion coefficient of hydrogen isotopes in lithium and yttrium as well as the mass transfer coefficient between a fluid and a solid pebble-bed are essential for the model to produce trustful results. For its validation, the developed numerical model is used to simulate the outcome of a deuterium retention experiment performed by Y. Yamasaki *et al.* [6]. Good accordance between simulation results and the experimental data demonstrate the accuracy of the simulation and thus create confidence to use this numerical model for the design of the hydrogen hot trap of IFMIF/DONES.

In the following paragraphs the term *hydrogen* will be used as a unified expression for all three hydrogen isotopes protium (P), deuterium (D) and tritium (T).

2. Numerical model of a hydrogen getter trap

To simulate the behaviour of an arbitrarily dimensioned yttrium pebble-bed in contact with hydrogen loaded flowing liquid lithium a numerical model has been developed and is presented in the following paragraphs. In our model the hydrogen hot trap is considered as a cylindrical hollow container with an entrance and an exit port located at the top and the bottom side of the cylinder. The container is densely filled with yttrium pebbles of radius r_{peb} , diameter d_{peb} and a surface of S_{peb} . The volume of the trap cylinder is fixed through the relation $V_{\text{trap}} = V_Y/\mu_{\text{pack}}$ where μ_{pack} is the packing density of the pebble-bed. The presented model is based on the assumption that no lithium or yttrium oxides are present in the system. Yttrium oxide layers formed around the pebble surfaces would act as hydrogen diffusion barriers and drastically slow down the retention process [8]. For the qualification of the performance of the hydrogen trap two quantities are defined. That is the trap efficiency:

$$\mu_{\text{trap}} = \frac{C_{\text{Li,in}} - C_{\text{Li,out}}}{C_{\text{Li,in}}} \quad (1)$$

where $C_{\text{Li,in}}$ is the hydrogen concentration in the lithium at the entrance of the trap and $C_{\text{Li,out}}$ the hydrogen concentration in the lithium at the exit of the trap. The second defined quantity is the hydrogen retention rate of the pebble-bed which stands for the number of absorbed hydrogen isotopes per second. In the developed numerical model of the hydrogen hot trap the total hydrogen retention rate of the yttrium pebble-bed $\dot{n}_{\text{trap}}(t)$

is calculated as the sum of the retention rates of all yttrium pebbles. The time evolving retention rate of a single yttrium pebble $\dot{n}_{\text{peb}}(t)$ can be calculated by

$$\dot{n}_{\text{peb}}(t) = J_{\text{ret}}(t) \cdot S_{\text{peb}} = J_{\text{ret}}(t) \cdot \pi d_{\text{peb}}^2 \quad (2)$$

where $J_{\text{ret}}(t)$ is the hydrogen retention flux from the lithium into the yttrium pebble. As we will see later the retention flux is dependent on the hydrogen concentration in the lithium at the interface between yttrium and lithium. Since the concentration varies along the longitudinal z -axis of the cylindrical trap container the total retention rate is being calculated integrating over the retention fluxes of all pebbles. For a trap container with length l_{trap} that contains a number of $\#_{\text{peb}}$ yttrium pebbles we calculate:

$$\dot{n}_{\text{trap}}(t) = \#_{\text{peb}} \cdot \frac{\pi d_{\text{peb}}^2}{l_{\text{trap}}} \int_0^{l_{\text{trap}}} J_{\text{ret}}(z, t) dz. \quad (3)$$

In the lithium (Li) as well as in the yttrium (Y), hydrogen isotopes are transported by the diffusion process. Hence, the retention flux of hydrogen isotopes into the pebbles is equal to the diffusion flux of hydrogen isotopes in yttrium $J_{\text{dif,Y}}$ at the interface between yttrium and lithium

$$J_{\text{ret}}(z, t) = J_{\text{dif,Y}}(r = r_{\text{peb}}, z, t). \quad (4)$$

According to Fick's first law the diffusion flux is proportional to the concentration gradient of hydrogen isotopes in the yttrium pebble in radial direction

$$J_{\text{dif,Y}}(r, z, t) = -D_Y \frac{\partial C_Y(r, z, t)}{\partial r}. \quad (5)$$

The proportionality constant D_Y is the diffusion coefficient of hydrogen isotopes in yttrium. The interstitial atomic diffusion coefficient of hydrogen isotopes in metals follows an Arrhenius type temperature dependence [9]:

$$D = D_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_d}{R_{\text{gas}} T}\right) \quad [\text{m}^2/\text{s}], \quad (6)$$

with D_0 being a pre-exponential factor and E_d the activation energy of diffusion. The constant R_{gas} labels the ideal gas constant given in $[\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}]$. For our calculation we focus on a temperature region between 250 °C and 325 °C since this is the proposed operation temperature region of the impurity control system of the DONES liquid lithium loop [10]. As we will see later on higher temperatures lead to a lower trap efficiency. In several previous experimental campaigns the temperature dependence of the diffusion coefficient of protium in yttrium could be determined. The measurements were done applying different methods and covering different temperature intervals. A list of the determined diffusion coefficient relations found in the literature can be seen in table 1. When plotting the diffusion coefficient of protium in yttrium against temperature applying each relation from table 1 it becomes apparent that they lead to highly different temperature dependencies.

Diffusion coefficient [m ² /s]	Temperature range	References
$D_{P,Y} = 1.30 \times 10^{-8} \cdot \exp[-41800/(R_{\text{gas}}T)]$	470 °C – 850 °C	[11] (refers to [12])
$D_{P,Y} = 3 \times 10^{-2} \cdot \exp[-160000/(R_{\text{gas}}T)]$	687 °C – 887 °C	[13] (measured)
$D_{P,Y} = 3.76 \times 10^{-7} \cdot \exp[-45986/(R_{\text{gas}}T)]$	400 °C – 1100 °C	[14] (calculated using [15, 16, 17])
$D_{P,Li} = 1.30 \times 10^{-3} \cdot \exp[-104600/(R_{\text{gas}}T)]$	615 °C – 905 °C	[18] (measured)
$D_{P,Li} = 1.38 \cdot \exp[-162000/(R_{\text{gas}}T)]$	500 °C – 650 °C	[19] (measured)
$D_{P,Li} = 2.74 \times 10^{-13} \cdot 10^{-\frac{110}{T}} \cdot T^{1.737}$	367 °C – 727 °C	[20] (measured)
$D_{P,Li} = 9.16 \times 10^{-14} \cdot 10^{-\frac{110}{T}} \cdot T^{1.737}$	615 °C – 905 °C	[14] (calculated using [18, 21])

Table 1: Diffusion coefficients of protium in yttrium and lithium that are found in the literature.

Especially towards low temperatures, the diffusion values produced by the three relations differ by several orders of magnitude. This gives rise to the assumption that the inaccuracy of all determined relations is relatively high. In the numerical model presented in this article we choose to implement the diffusivity relation determined by J. B. Talbot et al. in 1979 [11]. The decision is based on the fact that the temperature interval in which the diffusion values were determined is closer to the temperature region of interest in comparison to the measurements performed by P. W. Fisher et al. in 1984 [13]. For the determination of the diffusivity relation J. B. Talbot et al used the data set of only one experimental campaign in which the diffusivity was determined for a high number of temperature values [12]. In contrast, R. E. Buxbaum et al. used the data sets of three different experiments with a very low number of different temperature steps each [14]. Due to this fact we evaluated the diffusivity relation of J. B. Talbot et al. to be most reliable for our application. The diffusion coefficients of deuterium and tritium in yttrium can be approximately determined through the isotope effect of hydrogen isotope diffusion in metal [22]:

$$\frac{D_{Y,P}}{D_{Y,T}} = \sqrt{\frac{M_T}{M_P}} \quad \& \quad \frac{D_{Y,P}}{D_{Y,D}} = \sqrt{\frac{M_D}{M_P}} \quad \& \quad \frac{D_{Y,D}}{D_{Y,T}} = \sqrt{\frac{M_T}{M_D}} \quad (7)$$

where M_i marks the molar masses of the hydrogen isotopes i . The strong temperature dependence of the resulting diffusion coefficients of protium, deuterium and tritium in yttrium are plotted in figure 1 and it appears that with rising temperature the diffusivity increases.

The time evolving concentration gradient $\partial_r C_Y(r, z, t)$ along the radial direction of a pebble is determined by Fick's second law in spherical coordinates, given by:

$$\frac{\partial C_Y(r, z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{D_Y}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r^2 \frac{\partial C_Y(r, z, t)}{\partial r} \right] = -\frac{\partial J_{\text{diff},Y}(r, z, t)}{\partial r}. \quad (8)$$

As a consequence of the radial symmetry of the yttrium pebbles the hydrogen concentration gradient at the centre of a pebble is always zero.

Figure 1: Temperature dependency of the diffusion coefficients for hydrogen isotopes in yttrium and lithium that are used in the numerical model presented in this work [11],[20].

This fact forms a Neumann boundary condition:

$$\frac{\partial C_Y(r = 0, z, t)}{\partial r} = 0. \quad (9)$$

In order to describe the boundary condition at the interface between an yttrium pebble and the lithium it is important to define the thermodynamic regime of the hydrogen-yttrium-lithium system which we consider for this model. The phase diagram of the yttrium-hydrogen (Y-H) binary system (see references [23, 24]) reveals that for low hydrogen concentrations the Y-H solution occurs in a single hexagonal-close-packed α -Y phase in which the hydrogen isotopes are interstitially dissolved in the metal lattice. Within the temperature region of interest (250 °C to 325 °C) the di-hydride phase β -YH_{2+x} begins

to form as soon as hydrogen concentrations surpass [25]

$$C_{Y_{\alpha+\beta}} > 26 \text{ at\%} \hat{=} 1.7 \times 10^4 \text{ mol/m}^3. \quad (10)$$

For concentration greater than

$$C_{Y_{\beta}} > 65 \text{ at\%} \hat{=} 9.3 \times 10^4 \text{ mol/m}^3, \quad (11)$$

the whole Y-H solid solution has transformed into the β -YH_{2±x} phase and consists exclusively of yttrium di-hydrides [26]. Concentrations $C_Y > C_{Y_{\beta}}$ lead to the formation of an yttrium trihydride γ -YH_{3-x} phase. The phase diagram of the lithium-hydrogen (Li-H) system (see reference [27]) reveals that within the relevant temperature region and for low concentration, hydrogen isotopes are dissolved as a solute [28] in the liquid lithium (known as the α -phase). For hydrogen concentrations greater than

$$C_{Li_{\alpha+\beta}} > 1.5 \text{ at\%} \hat{=} 1 \times 10^3 \text{ mol/m}^3, \quad (12)$$

lithium-hydride (LiH) compounds begin to form which precipitate out as a solid (known as the β -phase).

From the DONES safety regulations we know that the tritium inventory in the lithium loop of DONES will be kept below 0.3 g. With a total lithium volume in the loop of approximately $V_{\text{loop}} \approx 10 \text{ m}^3$ this corresponds to a maximum tritium concentration of $C_{LiT,\text{max}} = 0.01 \text{ mol/m}^3$. The calculated generation rates of P, D and T in the DONES lithium loop reveals that the generation of 0.3 g tritium is accompanied by an accumulation of 0.2 g hydrogen and 6.67 g deuterium in the loop system [29]. Assuming that the hydrogen retention efficiency of the DONES hydrogen hot trap will be similar for all three isotopes we can conservatively estimate that the maximum hydrogen isotope inventory in the lithium loop will probably be maintained below 10 g. This would correspond to a maximum hydrogen isotope concentration in the loop of the order of $C_{LiH-\text{isot},\text{max}} \approx 0.5 \text{ mol/m}^3$ which is far smaller than the concentration $C_{Li_{\alpha+\beta}}$. For this reason and since the purpose of this work is the development of a model usable as a simulation tool for the design of the hydrogen hot trap for DONES, we consider the Li-H system in our model to be in the state of a low concentration α -phase.

The hydrogen concentration in the yttrium at the pebble surface is defined by a Dirichlet boundary condition. It is specified through the fact that in an infinitesimal area traversing the Y-Li interface the hydrogen solution remains always in chemical equilibrium. This implies an equality of the equilibrium pressures indicated by the pressure-composition-isotherms of the Li-H solution and of the Y-H solution [30, 31, 32]. For the low concentration region of the α -phase of a metal-hydrogen system the equilibrium pressures are determined by the Sieverts' law [33]:

$$C = K_s \cdot \sqrt{P_{\text{eq}}} \quad (13)$$

Here, K_s labels the Sieverts' constant. It quantifies the solubility of hydrogen isotopes in the corresponding metal. Since in this model the considered hydrogen concentration in the lithium is very low, the Sieverts' law should be valid for the

Li-H systems. For now we assume that the establishing hydrogen concentration in the yttrium pebbles is small compared to the concentration $C_{Y_{\alpha+\beta}}$ indicated in (10) and we suppose the Sieverts' law to be valid as well. In this case, the chemical equilibrium at the Y-Li interface can be expressed by

$$\sqrt{P_{\text{eq}_{Y-H}}} = \sqrt{P_{\text{eq}_{Li-H}}} \iff \frac{C_{Li}}{K_{s_{Li}}}\Big|_{\text{int}} = \frac{C_Y}{K_{s_Y}}\Big|_{\text{int}}. \quad (14)$$

Also the Sieverts' constant follows an Arrhenius type temperature dependence:

$$K_s = K_{s,0} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_s}{R_{\text{gas}}T}\right). \quad (15)$$

Here, $K_{s,0}$ is a pre-exponential factor and E_s the enthalpy of formation per dissolved mole of the solution. In several experimental campaigns temperature relations for the Sieverts' constant of hydrogen isotopes in lithium and yttrium could be determined. Depending on the applied experimental methods the different authors report their determined relations in different unit systems. In this work the SI-unit [$\text{mol/m}^3 \cdot \text{Pa}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$] is used for the Sieverts' constants. The SI-unit of the enthalpy of formation used in this article is [$\text{J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$]. Table 2 presents a list of determined values for $K_{s,0}$ and E_s that could be found in literature describing the solubility of hydrogen isotopes in yttrium. In table 3 the same coefficients are shown which were found in literature for hydrogen isotopes dissolved in lithium. To enable a direct comparison between the values of $K_{s,0}$ and E_s the coefficients are presented in every units system that was used in the different articles. If an asterisk is attached to a citation in the reference column it means that the respective article reported the corresponding coefficient in the unit system of the table row where the asterisk is placed. To convert the relations from the different unit systems to SI-units specific conversion factors are needed. The conversion factors of the pre-exponential factors in table 2 contain the molar mass of yttrium $M_Y = 88.906 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ and the density of yttrium $\rho_Y = 4472 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The molar mass of lithium that appears in the conversion factors of the pre-exponential factors in table 3 is $M_{Li} = 6.94 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$. For the density of lithium we use the relation $\rho_{Li}(T) = 562 - 0.1 \cdot T [\text{kg m}^{-3}]$ [45]. When plotted against temperature it is found that the Sieverts' constants $K_{s_{Li}}$ and K_{s_Y} that arise from the presented coefficients in table 2 and table 3 differ merely within one order of magnitude at any given temperature. Therefore, we can assume that the determined values are relatively accurate. For our calculations we make use of the solubility relation for hydrogen isotopes in yttrium which were measured by G. M. Begun *et al.* in 1980 in a high temperature measurement for all three isotopes [34]. Their experimental results are conform with a low temperature solubility measurement of the tritium-yttrium-system performed by S. D. Clinton *et al.* in 1979 [35]. Hence, G. M. Begun *et al.* concluded that his determined Sievert's relations seem to be applicable in both temperature ranges between 250 °C and 1000 °C. For the solubility of hydrogen isotopes in liquid lithium this numerical study makes use of the Sieverts' constants which were determined

	P in Y	D in Y	T in Y	Conversion factor	References
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{atom ratio}}{\sqrt{\text{Torr}}} \right]$	3.37×10^{-5}	3.76×10^{-5}	4.79×10^{-5}	$\frac{\rho_Y}{M_Y} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{760}{101325}}$	[34]* (measured)
	-	-	1.63×10^{-5}		[35] (measured)
	8.82×10^{-5}	-	-		[34]* (calculated using [31])
	7.05×10^{-5}	-	-		[35] (calculated using [31])
	-	2.23×10^{-5}	-		[36] (refers to [35])
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{atom ratio}}{\sqrt{\text{Pa}}} \right]$	2.92×10^{-6}	2.26×10^{-6}	4.15×10^{-6}	$\frac{\rho_Y}{M_Y}$	[34] (measured)
	-	-	1.41×10^{-6}		[35] (measured)
	7.64×10^{-6}	-	-		[34] (calculated using [31])
	6.11×10^{-6}	-	-		[35] (calculated using [31])
	-	2.92×10^{-6}	-		[36]* (refers to [35])
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{wppm}}{\sqrt{\text{Torr}}} \right]$	0.382	0.852	1.628	$\frac{10^{-6} \cdot \rho_Y}{M_{\text{H-isot}}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{760}{101325}}$	[34] (measured)
	-	-	0.55		[35]* (measured)
	0.999	-	-		[34] (calculated using [31])
	0.8	-	-		[35]* (calculated using [31])
	-	0.504	-		[36] (refers to [35])
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right]$	0.147	0.164	0.209	1	[34] (measured)
	-	-	0.071		[35] (measured)
	0.384	-	-		[34] (calculated using [31])
	0.307	-	-		[35] (calculated using [31])
	-	0.097	-		[36] (refers to [35])
$E_s \left[\frac{\text{cal}}{\text{mol} \cdot \text{K}} \right]$	23220	22710	21700	cal	[34]* (measured)
	-	-	22900		[35]* (measured)
	20930	-	-		[34]* (calculated using [31])
	21300	-	-		[35]* (calculated using [31])
	-	20903	-		[36] (refers to [35])
$E_s \left[\frac{\text{J}}{\text{mol} \cdot \text{K}} \right]$	97152	95019	90793	1	[34] (measured)
	-	-	95814		[35] (measured)
	87571	-	-		[34] (calculated using [31])
	89119	-	-		[35] (calculated using [31])
	-	87457	-		[36]* (refers to [35])

Table 2: Pre-exponential factors $K_{s,0}$ and activation energies E_s of the Arrhenius' type equations for hydrogen Sieverts' constant in yttrium.

by F. J. Smith *et al.* in 1979 [37] for all three hydrogen isotopes. The temperature dependence of the Sieverts' constant for hydrogen isotopes dissolved in liquid lithium and yttrium is plotted in figure 2. We see that in yttrium as well as in lithium the solubility of hydrogen isotopes decreases with temperature. In yttrium the solubility is several orders of magnitudes higher than in lithium. The difference between the solubilities even increases towards lower temperatures.

At this point we define a new quantity, the partitioning coefficient of the yttrium-lithium-system:

$$K_{d_{\text{Y-Li}}} \equiv \frac{K_{s_{\text{Y}}}}{K_{s_{\text{Li}}}}. \quad (16)$$

Its value mainly determines how efficient the retention mechanism of hydrogen isotopes from lithium into yttrium will be. Using the chosen Sieverts' relations given in the SI-unit system allows calculating the partitioning coefficients for the corresponding isotopes as done for the creation of figure 3. Sub-

stituting equation (16) into relation (14) allows expressing the boundary condition at the Y-Li interface as follows:

$$C_{\text{Y}}(r_{\text{peb}}, z, t) = K_{d_{\text{Y-Li}}} \cdot C_{\text{Li}}(z, t) \quad (17)$$

Here, $C_{\text{Li}}(z, t)$ stands for the hydrogen concentration in the lithium close to the pebble boundary layers.

Using equation (17) we calculate the hydrogen concentration in the yttrium that we would find at the pebble interface in case the estimated maximum hydrogen concentration $C_{\text{Li}} = 0.5 \text{ mol/m}^3$ was present in the lithium. Figure 3 reveals that in the temperature range from 250 °C to 325 °C the partitioning coefficient lies between $K_{d_{\text{Y-Li}}} \approx 4 \times 10^3$ and $K_{d_{\text{Y-Li}}} \approx 2 \times 10^4$. Hence, we determine a maximum hydrogen concentration in the yttrium of about $C_{\text{Y-H-isot,max}} \approx 1 \times 10^4 \text{ mol/m}^3$ at 250 °C. As the Y-H phase diagram and relation (10) indicate, at 250 °C this concentration corresponds to a Y-H system in the α -Y phase with no yttrium di-hydrides having formed yet. At higher temperature even lower concentrations would have established in

	P in Li	D in Li	T in Li	Conversion factor	References
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{atom ratio}}{\sqrt{\text{Torr}}} \right]$	5.32×10^{-5} 13.86×10^{-5} 5.48×10^{-5} 4.30×10^{-5} - 5.48×10^{-5} -	7.37×10^{-5} - 7.47×10^{-5} - - - 5.47×10^{-5}	9.84×10^{-5} - - 10.47×10^{-5} 9.87×10^{-5} -	$\frac{\rho_{\text{Li}}}{M_{\text{Li}}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{760}{101325}}$	[37]* (measured) [38] (measured) [39] (refers to [32, 40]) [41]* (refers to [42, 43]) [35] (refers to [37]) [44] (refers to [40]) [36] (refers to [32])
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{atom ratio}}{\sqrt{\text{atm}}} \right]$	1.47×10^{-3} 3.82×10^{-3} 1.51×10^{-3} 1.19×10^{-3} - 1.51×10^{-3} -	2.03×10^{-3} - 2.06×10^{-3} - - - 1.51×10^{-3}	2.71×10^{-3} - - 2.89×10^{-3} 2.72×10^{-3} -	$\frac{\rho_{\text{Li}}}{M_{\text{Li}}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{101325}}$	[37] (measured) [38] (measured) [39]* (refers to [32, 40]) [41] (refers to [42, 43]) [35] (refers to [37]) [44] (refers to [40]) [36] (refers to [32])
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{atom ratio}}{\sqrt{\text{Pa}}} \right]$	4.61×10^{-6} 1.20×10^{-5} 4.74×10^{-6} 3.72×10^{-6} - 4.73×10^{-6} -	6.38×10^{-6} - 6.47×10^{-6} - - - 4.74×10^{-6}	8.52×10^{-6} - - 9.07×10^{-6} 8.53×10^{-6} -	$\frac{\rho_{\text{Li}}}{M_{\text{Li}}}$	[37] (measured) [38]* (measured) [39] (refers to [32, 40]) [41] (refers to [42, 43]) [35] (refers to [37]) [44] (refers to [40]) [36]* (refers to [32])
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{wppm}}{\sqrt{\text{Torr}}} \right]$	7.73 20.13 7.95 6.25 - 7.93 -	21.39 - 21.68 - - - 15.88	42.76 - - 45.50 42.80 -	$\frac{10^{-6} \cdot \rho_{\text{Li}}}{M_{\text{H-isot}}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{760}{101325}}$	[37] (measured) [38] (measured) [39] (refers to [32, 40]) [41] (refers to [42, 43]) [35]* (refers to [37]) [44]* (refers to [40]) [36] (refers to [32])
$K_{s,0} \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{m}^3} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right]$	$\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 6.63 \times 10^{-4}$ $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 1.19 \times 10^{-2}$ $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 6.83 \times 10^{-4}$ $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 5.37 \times 10^{-4}$ - $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 6.81 \times 10^{-4}$ -	$\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 9.20 \times 10^{-4}$ - $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 9.32 \times 10^{-4}$ - - - $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 6.83 \times 10^{-4}$	$\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 1.23 \times 10^{-3}$ - - $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 1.31 \times 10^{-3}$ $\rho_{\text{Li}} \cdot 1.23 \times 10^{-3}$ -	1	[37] (measured) [38] (measured) [39] (refers to [32, 40]) [41] (refers to [42, 43]) [35] (refers to [37]) [44] (refers to [40]) [36] (refers to [32])
$E_s \left[\frac{\text{cal}}{\text{mol} \cdot \text{K}} \right]$	12404 10616 12285 12837 - 12285 -	11216 - 11049 - - - 12278	10105 - - 10075 10104 -	cal	[37] (measured) [38] (measured) [39] (refers to [32, 40]) [41] (refers to [42, 43]) [35]* (refers to [37]) [44] (refers to [40]) [36] (refers to [32])
$E_s \left[\frac{\text{J}}{\text{mol} \cdot \text{K}} \right]$	51898 44416 51400 53711 - 51400 -	46926 - 46227 - - - 51372	42279 - - 42154 42275 -	1	[37]* (measured) [38]* (measured) [39]* (refers to [32, 40]) [41]* (refers to [42, 43]) [35] (refers to [37]) [44]* (refers to [40]) [36]* (refers to [32])

Table 3: Pre-exponential factors $K_{s,0}$ and activation energies E_s of the Arrhenius' type equations of the hydrogen Sieverts' constant in lithium.

Figure 2: Temperature dependencies of the Sieverts' constants for hydrogen isotopes dissolved in yttrium and lithium that are used in the numerical model presented in this work [34, 37].

the yttrium. These findings give confidence to use the Sieverts' law for the calculation of the equilibrium pressures of the Y-H system in equation (14). If the maximum considered concentration in the lithium was higher, the Y-H system would very soon enter the β -phase in which yttrium di-hydrides start to form. In this case the Sievert's law would no longer be valid for the description of the pressure-composition-isotherms and equation (14) needed to be modified in order to ensure a reliable model. In the $\alpha + \beta$ phase transition region of the Y-H system the equilibrium pressure is identified as the plateau pressure of the pressure-composition-isotherms which for the Y-H system at 250 °C have not been determined so far [24]. Therefore, an extension of the model describing the retention process at concentrations $C_Y > C_{Y_{\alpha+\beta}}$ is not possible at this point. Studies like [26] or [46] discovered a formation of yttrium hydrides after an yttrium specimen was exposed to hydrogen loaded lithium. However, both experimental works observed the retention process into the yttrium at far higher hydrogen concentrations in the lithium than those which are considered in this study or expected for the IFMIF/DONES lithium loop.

In addition to equation (17) a further boundary condition at the Y-Li interface is given by the equality of particle fluxes on both sides of the interface. Since the hydrogen isotopes are dissolved in atomic form in the liquid metal as well as in the yttrium, neither recombination nor dissociation processes take place at the interface. Hence, only diffusion fluxes are governing the transport across the interface. Due to particle conservation the atomic diffusion flux $J_{MT}(z, t)$ on the lithium side of the interface must be equal to the atomic diffusion flux on the yttrium side of the interface $J_{diff,Y}(r_{peb}, z, t)$ and we write:

$$J_{diff,Y}(r_{peb}, z, t) = J_{MT}(z, t). \quad (18)$$

Figure 3: Temperature dependence of the partitioning coefficient for the hydrogen-lithium-yttrium-system calculated using the chosen Sieverts' constant relations presented in figure 2 [34, 37].

In the following we call J_{MT} the mass transfer diffusion flux of hydrogen isotopes in the liquid lithium at the Y-Li boundary layer. The mass transfer flux is quantified by Fick's first law, meaning it is proportional to the concentration gradient of hydrogen in lithium at the Y-Li interface. However, it would require an extensive numerical three dimensional calculation to determine the exact concentration profile which is present in the lithium flow through the interstitials of a pebble-bed. It is therefore approximated by assuming that the lithium flow leads to a mostly homogeneous concentration C_{Li} in the lithium which decreases drastically within a small layer of width d_{BL} around a pebble surface. The concentration decreases until it reaches its lowest value C_{LiLi} at the Y-Li interface. Figure 4 shows a sketch of the hydrogen concentration distribution in the one dimensional system of an yttrium pebble surrounded by flowing liquid lithium. Using Fick's first law and assuming a linear drop of the hydrogen concentration within the boundary layer of a pebble allows writing a formula for the mass transfer flux on the lithium side of the lithium-yttrium interface

$$J_{MT}(z, t) = \alpha_f \cdot [C_{Li}(z, t) - C_{LiLi}(z, t)] \quad (19)$$

where $\alpha_f \equiv D_{Li}/d_{BL}$ stands for the mass transfer coefficient. The parameter D_{Li} is the diffusion coefficient of hydrogen isotopes in the liquid lithium. For a pebble-bed the mass transfer coefficient could be estimated by E. J. Wilson and C. J. Geankopolis [47] using the equation:

$$\alpha_f \equiv 0.25 \cdot \frac{D_{Li}}{\epsilon \cdot d_{peb}} \cdot Re^{0.69} Sc^{1/3} \quad (20)$$

where ϵ is the porosity of the yttrium pebbles. In this model we consider a porosity of $\epsilon = 0.5$. For the Reynolds number Re

Figure 4: One dimensional system of an yttrium pebble surrounded by flowing liquid lithium showing the governing flux equations and a qualitative snapshot of the time evolving hydrogen concentration distribution in the yttrium bulk and in the liquid lithium.

and the Schmidt number Sc we make use of the expressions:

$$Re = \frac{\epsilon d_{peb} l_{trap}}{\mu_{Li}} \cdot \frac{F_{Li}}{V_{Li,trap}} \quad \& \quad Sc = \frac{\mu_{Li} \cdot D_{Li}}{d_{peb}}. \quad (21)$$

The parameter μ_{Li} is the dynamic viscosity of the lithium, F_{Li} the volumetric flow rate and $V_{Li,trap}$ the volume of liquid lithium in the trap container sitting in the interstitials between the pebbles. Table 1 presents a list of different relations for the diffusion coefficient D_{Li} that were found in the literature. All relations were determined in measurements covering different temperature ranges. Since this work is focused on system temperatures below 400 °C we choose to apply the diffusivity relation determined by H. Moriyama et al. [20]. Its temperature dependence is plotted in figure 1. The plot shows that hydrogen diffuses much quicker in lithium than in yttrium. As equation (2) reveals, the calculation of the hydrogen isotope retention rate of the yttrium pebbles requires the determination of the retention flux which is present at the interface of the yttrium pebbles. Substituting equation (18) and boundary condition (17) into equation (19) leads to the relation:

$$J_{dif,Y}(r_{peb}, z, t) = \alpha_f \cdot \left[C_{Li}(z, t) - \frac{C_Y(r_{peb}, z, t)}{K_{dY-Li}} \right]. \quad (22)$$

The time evolution of the hydrogen concentration $C_{Li}(z, t)$ in the liquid lithium that changes along the longitudinal axis of the trap container far away from the Y-Li boundary layer is described using the total time derivative:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dC_{Li}(z, t)}{dt} &= \frac{\partial C_{Li}(z, t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial C_{Li}(z, t)}{\partial z} \frac{\partial z}{\partial t} \\ &= -\frac{\#_{peb} \cdot S_{peb}}{V_{Li}} \cdot J_{dif,Y}(R, z, t) - \frac{F_{Li} \cdot l_{trap}}{V_{Li}} \cdot \frac{\partial C_{Li}(z, t)}{\partial z}. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Figure 5: Illustration of the diffusion direction into an yttrium pebble in two dimensions as well as the applied discretization of the radial direction.

Equation (5), (8), (9), (22) and (23) form a system of coupled differential and algebraic equations. Solving this system would provide the time evolution of $C_Y(r, z, t)$, $C_{Li}(z, t)$ and $C_{Li,Li}(z, t)$, as well as of the diffusion flux at the interface and in the pebbles $J_{dif,Y}(r, z, t)$. This would enable calculating the trap efficiency (1) and the total hydrogen isotope retention rate (2) of the pebble-bed. The only reasonable method to solve the presented system of coupled differential equations is a numerical finite difference approach. Therefore, the radial direction of each pebble is discretized into Q discretization nodes $j = 1, \dots, Q$ with $r_1 = 0$ m, $r_Q = r_{peb}$, $r_{j+1} = r_j + \Delta r$ and $Q = r_{peb}/\Delta r + 1$ (see figure 5). The numerical model of the pebble-bed is built on the assumption that in radial direction of the cylindrical trap container the calculated quantities are constant and only vary in the longitudinal z -direction. For the finite difference approach the trap container is segmented using the discretization nodes $z_n = z_1 \dots z_N$ (see figure 6). The time is discretized according to $t_{i+1} = t_i + \Delta t$. These definitions allow writing the system of algebraic and differential equations in their finite difference form which is presented below:

1. Fick's first (5) law describing the diffusion flux in radial direction everywhere inside of the pebble:

$$J_{dif,Y}(r_j, z_n, t_i) = -\frac{D_Y}{\Delta r} \cdot C_Y(r_{j+1}, z_n, t_i) - C_Y(r_j, z_n, t_i) \quad (24)$$

2. Boundary condition (9) providing the concentration for the node r_1 at the centre of a pebble. Its numerical finite difference representation can be found in the reference [48]:

$$\begin{aligned} C_Y(r_1, z_n, t_{i+1}) &= C_Y(r_1, z_n, t_i) + \\ &+ \frac{\Delta t \cdot 6D_Y}{\Delta r^2} [C_Y(r_2, z_n, t_i) - C_Y(r_1, z_n, t_i)] \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Figure 6: Discretization of the longitudinal z -direction of the cylindrical pebble-bed container.

3. Fick's second law (8) describing the time evolution of the concentration profile in radial direction of a pebble for the nodes r_2 to r_{Q-1} [48]. :

$$C_Y(r_j, z_n, t_{i+1}) = C_Y(r_j, z_n, t_i) + \frac{D_Y}{j-1} \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta r^2} \cdot [j \cdot C_Y(r_{j+1}, z_n, t_i) - 2(j-1) \cdot C_Y(r_j, z_n, t_i) + (j-2) \cdot C_Y(r_{j-1}, z_n, t_i)] \quad (26)$$

4. Fick's second law (8) expressed by the continuity equation used to describe the time evolution of the concentration for r_Q at the Y-Li interface:

$$C_Y(r_Q, z_n, t_{i+1}) = C_Y(r_Q, z_n, t_i) - \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta r} \cdot [J_{\text{dif},Y}(r_{Q-1}, z_n, t_i) - J_{\text{dif},Y}(r_Q, z_n, t_i)] \quad (27)$$

5. Boundary condition (22) providing the link between the hydrogen concentration in the yttrium and the concentration in the liquid lithium at the Y-Li interface:

$$C_Y(r_Q, z_n, t_i) = K_{\text{d}_{Y-Li}} \cdot \left[C_{\text{Li}}(z_n, t_i) - \frac{J_{\text{dif},Y}(r_Q, z_n, t_i)}{a_f} \right] \quad (28)$$

6. Total time derivative (23) of the hydrogen concentration in the lithium describing its variation in time and space along the z -axis of the trap:

$$C_{\text{Li}}(z_n, t_{i+1}) = C_{\text{Li}}(z_n, t_i) + \Delta t \cdot \left\{ \frac{\#_{\text{peb}} \cdot S_{\text{peb}}}{V_{\text{Li}}} \cdot J_{\text{dif},Y}(r_Q, z_n, t_i) - \frac{F_{\text{Li}} \cdot N}{V_{\text{Li}}} \cdot [C_{\text{Li}}(z_{n+1}, t_i) - C_{\text{Li}}(z_n, t_i)] \right\} \quad (29)$$

Determining the unknown variables of the system of equations in each discretization node requires an equal amount of equations and unknowns. To fulfil this, the initial values of the hydrogen concentrations $C_{\text{Li}}(z_n, t_1)$ and $C_Y(r_{j-1}, z_n, t_1)$ in

the lithium and in the yttrium need to be known. The input concentration in the lithium at the entrance of the trap $C_{\text{Li},\text{in}} \equiv C_{\text{Li}}(z_1, t_i)$ can be seen as the input parameter of the trap system and hence needs to be given for each instance in time. As an output parameter of the trap system we obtain the concentration $C_{\text{Li},\text{out}} \equiv C_{\text{Li}}(z_N, t_i)$.

For the treatment of the equations (25) - (29) in this work the non-causal programming software EcosimPro is used which is capable of solving large systems of coupled differential and algebraic equations [49].

3. Simulation results and discussion

In this section first simulation results are presented which demonstrate the response of the Y-trap model when connecting it to a simplified liquid lithium loop system. We consider the case in which the trap exit is connected with the trap entrance by a pipe of length l_{pipe} . The time and space variation of the hydrogen isotope concentration in the liquid lithium which is flowing through the connecting pipe is described using the total time derivative (23). Therefore, the pipe length is subdivided by the discretization nodes $z_m = z_1, \dots, z_M$ allowing a finite difference expression of (23) similar to equation (29):

$$C_{\text{Li,pipe}}(z_m, t_{i+1}) = C_{\text{Li,pipe}}(z_m, t_i) - \Delta t \cdot \frac{F_{\text{Li}} \cdot M}{V_{\text{Li}}} \cdot [C_{\text{Li,pipe}}(z_{m+1}, t_i) - C_{\text{Li,pipe}}(z_m, t_i)] \quad (30)$$

The fact that no retention flux is present in the tube explains why the first term of equation (29) does not appear in this expression. For a complete numerical description of the new system containing the trap and the pipe, equation (30) needs to be added to the system of equations (25) - (29). The trap and the pipe are linked through the conditions $C_{\text{Li},\text{in}}(t_i) = C_{\text{Li,pipe}}(z_M, t_i)$ and $C_{\text{Li},\text{out}}(t_i) = C_{\text{Li,pipe}}(z_1, t_i)$. Adding these equations to the system (25) - (29) finally leads to an equal amount of equations and unknowns making its solution unique. Only the free parameters of the loop-pebble-bed system as well as the initial hydrogen concentration in every discretization point of the different media needs to be chosen in advance.

3.1. Case A: Finite initial H-isotope concentration

As a parameter study of the numerical model we simulate a loop system containing $V_{\text{Li}} = 1 \text{ m}^3$ of liquid lithium heated to $T = 300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The loop system is connected with a cylindrical trap container of width $d_{\text{trap}} = 5 \text{ cm}$ which is densely filled with 1 kg of $d_{\text{peb}} = 1 \text{ mm}$ pebbles. The packing density is assumed to be 50% resulting in a trap length of $l_{\text{trap}} = 23 \text{ cm}$. The volume flow rate of the lithium is chosen to be $F_{\text{Li}} = 11/\text{s}$. The initial hydrogen isotope concentration in the liquid lithium shall be $C_{\text{Li},\text{init}} = 1 \text{ mol/m}^3$ for each isotope P, D and T while the yttrium pebbles have no initial hydrogen inventory. The chosen numbers of the spacial discretization nodes are $N = 5$, $M = 5$ and $Q = 101$. The simulation is performed for 4320 time steps of $\Delta t = 10 \text{ s}$, hence calculating the system behaviour for the first 12 h. Using equation (16) and

Figure 7: Simulated time evolution of the tritium concentration profile in a pebble of the first segment of the discretized trap.

the chosen relations for the Sieverts' constants we find the following partitioning coefficients for the different isotopes:

$$K_{d_{Y-Li-P}} = 5836, \quad K_{d_{Y-Li-D}} = 8517, \quad K_{d_{Y-Li-T}} = 8879. \quad (31)$$

In figure 7 the simulated time evolution of the tritium concentration in an yttrium pebble of the first trap segment $z_{n=1}$ is plotted for different moments in time. We see how the particles diffuse towards the centre of the pebbles, while particles keep entering into the pebble surfaces. After 12 h the concentration gradients vanish which causes the retention flux to disappear. In figure 8 the average protium, deuterium and tritium concentration in the liquid lithium is plotted against time. We see that the concentrations decrease instantaneously until they finally reach an equilibrium concentration. In chemical equilibrium the concentration gradients in the lithium and the yttrium have decreased to zero. The equilibrium concentration establishes when the chemical potential of the hydrogen isotopes in the lithium is equal to that in the yttrium, meaning that $C_Y = K_{d_{Y-Li}} \cdot C_{Li}$ is valid in the whole system. It can be analytically calculated combining this equilibrium condition with the particle conservation relation $n_{tot} = n_{Li,eq} + n_{Y,eq}$ which relates the amount of particles in the lithium at $t = 0$ s with the particle amount distribution in the lithium and the yttrium in the moment of equilibrium. We find:

$$C_{Li,eq} = \frac{C_{Li,init} \cdot V_{Li}}{V_{Li} + \frac{m_Y}{\rho_Y} \cdot K_{d_{Y-Li}}}. \quad (32)$$

Using this equation we calculate the equilibrium concentration for each isotope and we find $C_{Li,P,eq} = 0.43 \text{ mol/m}^3$, $C_{Li,D,eq} = 0.34 \text{ mol/m}^3$, $C_{Li,T,eq} = 0.33 \text{ mol/m}^3$. As we can see in figure 8 the numerically calculated equilibrium concentrations conform with the concentrations calculated using equation (32).

Figure 8: Simulated time evolution of the average hydrogen isotope concentration in 1 m^3 of liquid lithium at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ flowing through a pebble-bed containing 1 kg of 1 mm yttrium pebbles.

3.2. Case B: Zero initial concentration & tritium generation

In the following simulation we consider a constant generation of tritium isotopes in the liquid lithium flow with generation rate of $n_{T,gen} = 1 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mol s}^{-1}$ while the initial concentration of hydrogen isotopes is zero in the lithium as well as in the yttrium. All other parameters are the same as in the previous case. The generation of tritium in the lithium is considered to happen in the first segment $m = 1$ of the tube that connects the input and output of the hydrogen trap. It is introduced in the model by modifying equation (30) adding a generation term only for $m = 1$:

$$C_{Li,pipe}(z_1, t_{i+1}) = C_{Li,pipe}(z_1, t_i) - \Delta t \cdot \left\{ \frac{M}{V_{Li}} \cdot n_{T,gen} - \frac{F_{Li} \cdot M}{V_{Li}} \cdot [C_{Li,pipe}(z_1, t_i) - C_{Li,pipe,in}(t_i)] \right\} \quad (33)$$

In figure 9 the simulated tritium concentration profile inside of a 1 mm wide yttrium pebble is plotted for different instances in time assuming a pebble-bed of mass $m_Y = 1 \text{ kg}$. Since at the lithium-yttrium-interface the chemical equilibrium condition (14) is fulfilled at any time and since we consider a constant tritium generation in the lithium, the tritium concentration at the yttrium surface starts to rise with time. Simultaneously, the tritium moves towards the centre of the pebble. We observe that after about 7 h the concentration gradients along the radius seem to not change anymore which results in a constant retention flux. This explains why the concentration in the yttrium rises homogeneously along the radius and almost proportional with time.

In case no hydrogen trap is connected to the loop the average tritium concentration in the lithium would rise linearly

Figure 9: Simulated time evolution of the tritium concentration profile in 1 mm wide yttrium pebbles that form part of an yttrium pebble-bed of $m_Y = 1$ kg. For this simulation a constant generation of tritium atoms is considered in the liquid lithium.

Figure 10: Simulated time evolution of the average tritium concentration in 1 m^3 of liquid lithium considering a constant tritium generation in the loop and different masses of the yttrium pebble-bed.

with time as we can see in figure 10 where the average tritium concentration is simulated for the first 24 hours. The other three curves in figure 10 show the tritium concentration in the lithium averaged over the length of the loop when an yttrium pebble-bed is connected to the flow considering a total yttrium mass of either $m_Y = 1$ kg, $m_Y = 2$ kg or $m_Y = 3$ kg in the trap cylinder. In general we observe that more yttrium pebbles lead to a stronger retention of tritium from the lithium into the pebbles. However, after about 7 h for all three pebble-bed masses the concentration in the lithium seems to rise linearly and does not approach a steady state in which the generation rate would be equal to the retention rate. It is to mention that in a steady state scenario in which the concentration in the lithium would not rise anymore the pebbles would tend to establish a homogeneous concentration profile causing the retention flux to decrease. This would then move the system out of the steady state causing the concentration in the lithium to rise again. Therefore, it is impossible to reach steady state even for the biggest imaginable pebble-bed. Using more yttrium pebbles only slows down the concentration increase in the liquid lithium. As figure 9 exhibits the retention flux into the pebbles becomes constant after time. As soon as this equilibrium state has been reached for the pebbles in each trap segment we observe that the difference between input and output concentration $C_{\text{Li,in}} - C_{\text{Li,out}}$ of the trap becomes constant as well. However, because the input concentration $C_{\text{Li,in}}$ will always rise the trap efficiency has to sink according to equation (1). In figure 11 the simulated trap efficiency is plotted considering different masses of the yttrium pebble-bed. We find that as expected for bigger yttrium masses the efficiency is bigger and drops slower than for smaller masses. In figure 12 the

average tritium concentration in the lithium is plotted against time when executing the simulations taking into account different lithium temperatures ($T = 250^\circ\text{C}$, $T = 300^\circ\text{C}$ and $T = 350^\circ\text{C}$) and a pebble-bed of $m_Y = 1$ kg. Although the diffusion coefficient of hydrogen isotopes in lithium and yttrium is smaller for lower temperatures the partitioning coefficient of the hydrogen-yttrium-lithium system increases drastically moving from $T = 350^\circ\text{C}$ to $T = 250^\circ\text{C}$ (see figure 3). This explains why in figure 11 tritium is retained much more efficiently from the lithium at lower lithium temperatures. However, the trap efficiency does not only depend on the yttrium mass and the temperature. The retention flux at the pebble interface exhibits a linear relation with the mass transfer coefficient α_f in equation (22). Beside its dependency on the temperature, the mass transfer coefficient is dependent on the pebble diameter, the trap length and the volumetric flow rate. We find that for higher flow rates as well as for smaller yttrium pebbles and longer trap cylinders, the mass transfer coefficient increases which leads to a higher retention flux. It is to mention that varying these parameters within the same order of magnitude has almost no effect on the retention rate of the trap when considering bigger time scales. Their variation shows its greatest impact on the time after which the trap starts to exhibit its full potential where the retention flux is highest. This state is reached when the concentration gradients along the pebble radii are steepest and reach a constant state in every segment n of the trap. Therefore, the first tritium atoms need to have reach the pebble centre. The required time for this to occur is logically higher for larger pebbles. As visible in figure 9, for pebbles with $d_{\text{peb}} = 1$ mm the state of constant concentration gradients in the pebble is reached after about 7 h. Figure 10 shows how this time coincides with the

Figure 11: Simulated time evolution of the trap efficiency considering a constant tritium generation in the loop and different pebble-bed masses.

moment the lithium concentration starts to increase linearly and slower than before. In figure 13 the average concentration in the liquid lithium is shown for a pebble-bed of $d_{\text{peb}} = 1$ mm, $d_{\text{peb}} = 5$ mm and $d_{\text{peb}} = 10$ mm maintaining all other parameters equal as in the first simulation. For 5 mm pebbles the concentration curve exhibits a constant slope after about 1 week and in case of 10 mm pebbles after about 4 weeks. The final slope of the concentration increase tends to be the same for different pebble diameters and only depend on the total yttrium mass. A pebble-bed containing smaller yttrium pebbles leads to a final concentration in the lithium which is below the final concentration that establishes in case of bigger pebbles. Hence, a hydrogen trap is most efficient when the lithium is as cold as possible but above its melting point, when the mass of the pebble-bed is as high as possible and when the pebble diameter is as small as technologically reasonable.

3.3. Validation of the numerical model

In order to validate the presented numerical model of a getter pebble-bed the measurement results of a deuterium retention experiment performed in the past by Y. Yamasaki et al. are simulated [6]. Their experimental system consists of a storage tank where 600 g of molten lithium is charged with deuterium up to a concentration of $C_{\text{D,Li}}(t_0) = 160$ wppm ≈ 40.1 mol/m³. Subsequently, it is pumped into a small loop system where its temperature is kept at $T = 300$ °C. In the circuit the liquid lithium is driven by an electromagnetic pump (EMP), thus flowing through a miniature yttrium pebble-bed of length 300 mm which is connected in line with the loop. For the experiment the lithium volumetric flow rate is adjusted to 25 ml s⁻¹. The trap is filled with 10 g of 2 mm – 3 mm wide yttrium chips. While the lithium is circulating through the

Figure 12: Simulated time evolution of the average tritium concentration in 1 m³ of liquid lithium considering a constant tritium generation in the loop and different system temperatures.

trap the yttrium pebbles absorb the deuterium dissolved in the lithium. During this process lithium samples are extracted at various instances in time and stored in a sample container. After each sample recovery the lithium probe is transferred to an experimental apparatus where the remaining deuterium concentration is measured using the chemical dissolution method [6, 50, 51]. In figure 14 the ratio between the measured concentrations and the initial concentration is plotted against the amount of lithium which has passed through the pebble-bed in the moment when the samples were recovered [6].

The tritium transport into the pebble-bed of this experimental system can be numerically simulated using the previously presented model. In its simplified form, the configuration of Y. Yamasaki's experiment is equivalent to the trap-pipe-system which has been numerically treated in subsection 3.1. Only the system parameters are adjusted to those of the experimental system. As pebble diameter we choose 1 mm since for a fix pebble-bed mass they exhibit the same total surface as 2 mm wide yttrium chips with a thickness of 0.5 mm. For the simulation we consider a 5 mm wide and 28 cm long trap container. The assumed yttrium packing density is 40%. In addition to the experimental data points the numerically simulated deuterium concentration ratio is plotted in figure 14 using a continuous line. The first simulation is performed assuming that all 600 g of the molten lithium have entered into the lithium loop. We see that the simulated concentration curve is conform with the first data point. Although the simulated curve stays slightly above the measured data points it proceeds very close to the second and third data point. As soon as about 100 l have passed the pebble-bed the simulated curve slowly flattens down approaching chemical equilibrium while the experimental values tend to drop even stronger than ever before reaching

Figure 13: Simulated time evolution of the average tritium concentration in 1 m^3 of liquid lithium considering a constant tritium generation in the loop with a pebble-bed of $m_Y = 1 \text{ kg}$ for different yttrium pebble diameters.

concentration ratios of $C_{\text{Li}}/C_{\text{Li,init}} \approx 0.010 \pm 0.009$. However, calculating the equilibrium concentration in the liquid lithium at $T = 300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using equation (32) reveals a minimum possible concentration ratio of $C_{\text{Li,eq}}/C_{\text{Li,init}} = 5.9 \times 10^{-2}$ which is conform with the behaviour of the simulated concentration ratio. Hence, not the model itself but another factor seems to be responsible for the inconsistency between experiment and simulation. The value of the equilibrium concentration is mainly determined by the partitioning coefficient $K_{\text{d}_{\text{Y-Li-D}}}$. For this simulation the value $K_{\text{d}_{\text{Y-Li-D}}} = 8517$ has been used after being calculated as the ratio of the Sieverts' constants of deuterium in yttrium and lithium at $T = 300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ reported by G. M. Begun et al. and F. J. Smith et al. in [34] and [37]. Not precisely measured Sieverts' constants could have resulted in an incorrectly calculated partitioning coefficient. This could explain the mismatch between simulation result and experiment. For the verification of the numerical model it needs to be taken into account that important information about the exact set-up of the experiment, its dimensions and its execution was not available and could therefore not be taken into account in the model with sufficient detail. Without the missing information an exact numerical reproduction of the experimental results is not possible. For example, the amount of lithium that was eventually in contact with the pebble-bed is unknown since only the total mass of molten lithium in the lithium storage tank has been reported in the reference article. The loop is filled by pressurising the space above the lithium surface in the storage tank with argon gas. As a result the lithium rises up through a thin pipe filling the loop system with liquid lithium while the lithium surface sinks down. The pipe inlet is located at the bottom of the storage tank. As soon as the sinking lithium surface reaches the pipe inlet the filling pro-

Figure 14: Simulated time evolution of deuterium inventory in 600 g of liquid lithium in contact with 10 g of yttrium discs at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in comparison with experimental values measured by Y. Yamasaki et al. that performed an experiment under similar conditions [6].

cess stops. This implies that some of the lithium will remain in the storage tank. Therefore, it is a very probable scenario that eventually less than 600 g of liquid lithium have entered the loop. In order to observe the influence of this scenario on the simulation results, the simulation is repeated assuming that only 500 g of lithium have entered the loop. We see that the simulated curve is now even closer to the experimentally determined values (see dashed line in figure 14). Moreover, information about the exact geometries of the trap container and the yttrium chips which play an important role for the simulation outcome were not available for the calculation. During the hydrogen retention process it is reasonable to assume that a not negligible amount of deuterium has diffused into the loop walls. This could explain why the last measured deuterium concentration is below the actual equilibrium value between yttrium and lithium.

Another reason for the faster decreasing experimentally determined concentrations in comparison with the simulation results might originate from a formation of yttrium di-hydrides and even yttrium tri-hydrides on the surface of the yttrium chips. This is a probable scenario, since the initial hydrogen concentration in the lithium is relatively high. Applying equation (17) with $K_{\text{d}_{\text{Y-Li-D}}} = 8517$ and $C_{\text{D,Li}}(t_0) \approx 40.1 \text{ mol/m}^3$ would yield a deuterium concentration in the yttrium which is far greater than the concentrations $C_{\text{Y}_{\alpha+\beta}}$ and $C_{\text{Y}_{\beta}}$ indicated by equation (10) and equation (11). Since the developed model is based on the assumption that all observed metal-hydride systems are present in their α -phases, the existence of metal-hydrides would reduce the models reliability. However, the finding that Y. yamasaki et al. observed a more efficient deuterium retention than predicted with our model could be an

indicator for the possibility that a formation of yttrium di- and tri-hydrides results in an acceleration of the gettering process of hydrogen isotopes into the yttrium.

In any case, we can say that it is difficult to validate the accuracy of the numerical model as long as the correctness of the single experimental parameters and especially the partitioning coefficient are not confirmed with sufficient certainty. Nevertheless, the model allows producing simulation results which are satisfyingly close to the experimental data.

4. Conclusion

In the presented work a numerical model has been developed from scratch capable of describing the hydrogen transport from flowing liquid metal into a getter pebble-bed. Especially the hydrogen retention from flowing liquid lithium by yttrium pebbles has been considered. The model focuses on solving the transport equations of the system taking into account the boundary conditions at the interfaces of the different media. The considered boundary conditions are based on the assumption that the Li-H system as well as the Y-H system are present in their α -phases. The model depends on the correctness of several experimental parameters that were determined in the past by different experimental campaigns. In this work the different values found in literature are compared and carefully chosen for their application in the model.

In a case study first simulation results are analysed. Therefore, a system is considered in which the inlet and the outlet of the trap is connected by a simple pipe. First the hydrogen transport is simulated in which the lithium contained in the trap and the pipe has a finite initial hydrogen isotope concentration while the initial concentration in the yttrium is zero. The shape of the concentration decrease in the lithium behaves as expected reaching a chemical equilibrium after a steep initial concentration drop. We find that the trap is most efficient for tritium, then deuterium and then protium. Then, a case is considered in which the initial concentrations are zero and tritium is generated in a constant manner. It is discovered that for higher yttrium masses the concentration increase in the loop is slowed down more efficiently but never reaches a stationary state in which the absorption flux is equal to the generation rate. Although after time the retention rate of the trap reaches a constant value the trap efficiency decreases very quickly since the general hydrogen concentration in the loop will always increase. Moreover, lower lithium temperatures significantly improve the trap efficiency in the temperature region from interest. A variation of all other free system variables have a minor impact on the trap behaviour.

In order to validate the accuracy of the trap model experimental data of a measurement performed by Y. Yamasaki *et al.* is reproduced in a numerical simulation. In their experiment deuterium loaded liquid lithium is flowing through a miniature yttrium pebble-bed. As a result the deuterium concentration in the lithium decreases which was measured at various points in time. For the numerical reproduction of the experimental results the boundary variables and the initial conditions of the experimental set-up are considered as input parameters of the

trap model. We find that the simulated concentration evolves very similar to the experimental values. However, the simulated concentration drop is slightly flatter leading to a growing difference between experimental and simulation results. This small systematic difference can probably be attributed to the fact that important information about the exact conditions and geometry of the experiment was not available. Also a possible formation of yttrium di-hydrides would have made the model less reliable for the numerical reproduction of the experimental data. Therefore, a higher correspondence between simulated and experimental results can not be expected.

For a more accurate and meaningful validation of the model another hydrogen retention experiment should be constructed and executed on site containing a lithium loop connected to a miniature yttrium pebble-bed. Thus, all necessary input parameters will be directly available with sufficient detail. In addition, it is necessary to more accurately measure the partitioning coefficient of hydrogen isotopes that establishes between yttrium and lithium within the temperature range of interest. In general we can say that the model forms a trustful tool to accurately simulate the hydrogen retention process from flowing liquid lithium into an yttrium pebble-bed.

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